
Assessment of the Current State and Future Prospects of Online Learning in Bangladesh's Education System

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Abstract

Online learning is redefining educational paradigms worldwide, with the potential to overcome traditional barriers and create accessible, flexible learning environments. Conducted from January 2023 to May 2023, this study presents a comprehensive examination of online learning in Bangladesh, integrating both quantitative and qualitative analyses to provide a multifaceted view of the phenomenon. Quantitative research reveals detailed patterns of online learning usage across various educational sectors, highlighting both advantages and notable challenges faced by 37.3% of respondents. Qualitative methods uncover the human dimensions of online learning, elucidating personal experiences, perceived benefits, and practical hurdles. Together, these analyses weave a nuanced picture of the online learning landscape in Bangladesh, recognizing its complexity and the dynamic interplay between statistical realities and human experiences. An undercurrent of optimism emerges, reflecting a collective belief in the potential for growth and innovation. The research, grounded in rigorous methodology and ethical considerations, offers critical insights and evidence-based guidance for shaping a more inclusive and effective online learning environment. The findings resonate not only within the Bangladeshi context but also in broader global frameworks, making a significant contribution to the burgeoning field of online education. By illuminating the intricacies of online learning in Bangladesh during this specific time period, this study sets the stage for informed policy-making, practical implementation, and future exploration, offering a valuable resource for educators, policymakers, and researchers seeking to harness the transformative potential of technology in education.

Keywords: Online Learning, E-Learning, Education System in Bangladesh, Distance Education

1 Introduction

In the era of digitization, the landscape of education has been significantly transformed by the advent of online learning. As the digital divide narrows, and accessibility to internet-enabled devices increases, the shift towards digital education has gained momentum worldwide. This transformation has been particularly evident in Bangladesh, a rapidly developing nation with a burgeoning young population. The COVID-19 pandemic served as a catalyst, accelerating the shift towards online learning, making it an indispensable part of the country's education system [1] [2]. In the face of school closures and social distancing measures, educational institutions in Bangladesh, like many others globally, resorted to online learning. The country has seen an

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unprecedented adoption of digital platforms for education, with both public and private institutions scrambling to transfer their academic activities online [3] [4]. However, the sudden shift, driven by necessity rather than strategic planning, has led to numerous challenges and exposed gaps in the system [5]. This paper, based on data collected between January 2023 and May 2023, explores these dynamics. Despite the challenges, this forced experiment has presented an opportunity to assess the potential of online learning in the context of Bangladesh's education system. Online learning holds promise for enhancing access to education, personalizing learning experiences, and providing flexibility to learners [6] [7]. Yet, questions remain regarding its effectiveness, acceptance, and sustainability in the long run. Building on this context, it is essential to understand that the shift towards online education in Bangladesh was not solely a reaction to the pandemic but part of a broader governmental effort to implement Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education [8]. The pandemic has intensified the importance of this effort, highlighting both its potential and the obstacles that must be overcome. Furthermore, the challenges brought about by the pandemic have had a profound global impact on the education sector, but the situation in Bangladesh offers a unique perspective. The experiences of three government colleges during the COVID-19 pandemic, as explored in the present study, provide valuable insights into the opportunities and hurdles faced by educational institutions in a developing country [9]. As Bangladesh continues to navigate the uncharted waters of online education, there is a growing need for strategic planning, collaboration, technological advancement, and pedagogical innovation. This paper seeks to contribute to the conversation by examining the specific context of Bangladesh, shedding light on the complexities and suggesting avenues for future development in the realm of digital education.

The study is significant for the following reasons:

1. **Enhancing understanding of online learning:** The findings of this study will contribute to a better understanding of the strengths and weaknesses of online learning in Bangladesh. This includes understanding how online learning has been implemented in the country, the effectiveness of various strategies, and the overall impact on students' learning outcomes.
2. **Informing education policy:** The results can inform policymakers about the current state of online learning and provide them with evidence-based recommendations for improving the online learning infrastructure, teaching methodologies, and policies in Bangladesh.
3. **Future planning:** By assessing the prospects of online learning, this research can help educational institutions, educators, and policymakers plan for a more integrated and effective use of digital technologies in teaching and learning processes. This could potentially lead to developing a more resilient education system that can adapt to unforeseen circumstances like the recent pandemic.
4. **Supporting learners and educators:** The insights from this study can guide learners and educators on how to optimally utilize online resources for education and highlight areas requiring additional support or training.

Against this backdrop, this research aims to delve into the current state of online learning in Bangladesh and explore its future prospects. The objectives of the study are twofold: Firstly, it seeks to evaluate the effectiveness, acceptance, and challenges of online learning in the present context. Secondly, it aspires to explore the feasibility of a sustained and strategic shift towards online learning post-pandemic, and the potential strategies for its effective implementation. This research seeks to contribute to the body of knowledge on online learning in Bangladesh and provide insights that could inform policy decisions, shape educational reforms, and ultimately ensure quality and inclusive education for all.

2 Literature Review

The dawn of digital technology has reshaped global educational landscapes, with online learning becoming a ubiquitous part of many education systems. Bangladesh's foray into this domain, however, is a relatively recent development and is a field with limited academic scrutiny. This literature review aims to delve deeper into this topic, reviewing the existing body of knowledge surrounding the state of online learning in Bangladesh and potential future trajectories.

2.1 The Advent and Acceleration of Online Learning

The arrival of Covid-19 triggered an abrupt shift in the modality of education delivery worldwide, Bangladesh being no exception [10]. The virus-induced closure of educational institutions necessitated a swift transition to remote learning. According to [11], these unprecedented circumstances thrust online learning to the forefront

of Bangladesh’s education system. However, the abruptness of this transition unveiled numerous challenges, some of which were unique to the context of Bangladesh.

2.2 Challenges in Implementing Online Learning

Online learning implementation in Bangladesh has been fraught with technological and infrastructural issues. Khan et al. [12] noted that many students, particularly those in rural areas, encountered difficulties in accessing the internet and lacked suitable devices for online learning. Shrestha, Sagun, et al.[13] further elaborated on these challenges, pointing out frequent power outages, inadequate bandwidth, and the prohibitive costs associated with internet usage. This, they argue, compromised the effectiveness of online learning.

Beyond technical and infrastructural hurdles, the literature points to several pedagogical challenges. For instance, Kabir, Humayun, et al. [14] found that a large proportion of teachers lacked the necessary digital literacy and pedagogical knowledge to deliver effective online instruction. This gap in teaching competency could potentially undermine the quality and effectiveness of online education.

2.3 Potential Benefits and Opportunities

While challenges are apparent, online learning also presents unique opportunities for Bangladesh’s education system. Akter, Farhina, et al.[15] posited that online learning could democratize education by providing increased accessibility and flexibility. This could be particularly impactful for specific demographics, such as working students, women, and individuals in geographically remote regions. Online learning, they argue, could play a significant role in furthering the country’s educational attainment rate. Moreover, the adaptability of online platforms allows for a personalized learning experience, catering to individual needs and pacing. This could foster a more student-centered approach, encouraging self-directed learning and critical thinking. The integration of multimedia resources and collaborative tools could enhance engagement and facilitate a more interactive learning experience. Additionally, online learning could pave the way for cross-border collaboration and global exposure, bridging the gap between local and international educational practices. However, realizing these potentials necessitates careful planning, investment in technological infrastructure, continuous training of educators, and a commitment to maintaining quality standards. The future of online education in Bangladesh rests not only on its technological readiness but also on its ability to align with cultural, pedagogical, and socio-economic factors that shape the learning experience.

2.4 The Role of Advanced Technologies

Recent research has begun to examine the role of emerging technologies in online learning. Ouyang, Fan, Luyi Zheng, and Pengcheng Jiao[16] and Seo [17] discussed the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning in providing personalized learning experiences, improving learner engagement, and enhancing educational outcomes. They contend that these advanced technologies could significantly enrich the online learning environment in Bangladesh, although this remains a relatively unexplored and underutilized area [18]. The application of AI and ML in education goes beyond the traditional classroom setting, as it has the potential to create adaptive learning pathways tailored to individual student needs. By analyzing a learner’s behavior and performance, AI-driven systems can recommend personalized content and exercises, adjust the level of difficulty, and provide immediate feedback, thus enabling a more engaged and effective learning experience. Furthermore, these technologies offer the prospect of automating administrative tasks for educators, such as grading and attendance tracking, allowing them to focus more on teaching and mentoring. They also open doors to the development of intelligent tutoring systems, which can act as supplementary instructors, providing assistance and guidance even outside regular school hours.

In the context of Bangladesh, the integration of AI and ML in online learning is particularly significant, considering the country’s ongoing efforts to digitalize education and reduce disparities in access to quality learning materials. While urban areas in Bangladesh have seen some advancements in integrating technology into education, rural areas still face challenges related to infrastructure and resources. The deployment of AI and ML can potentially bridge this gap by offering more accessible and affordable educational resources.

However, the implementation of these technologies also raises concerns, such as the need for substantial investments in infrastructure and training, potential biases in AI algorithms, and issues related to data privacy and security. There is also a risk of widening the digital divide if proper care is not taken to ensure that these innovations reach all segments of the population, including those with disabilities or other special needs.

Ongoing research and collaboration between educational institutions, technology companies, and policy-makers will be crucial in addressing these challenges and realizing the full potential of AI and ML in enhancing online learning. By fostering a supportive ecosystem that encourages innovation and inclusivity, Bangladesh

can position itself as a leader in the field of technology-driven education. The exploration of these technologies within the country's specific context is still in its nascent stages, and continued investment, research, and development will be essential for unlocking the myriad possibilities they offer.

2.5 Psychological Implications of Online Learning

As well as the technological and pedagogical aspects, the literature indicates that the psychological impact of online learning needs to be considered. Hasan, Najmul, and Yukun Bao [19] observed an increase in stress and anxiety levels among students transitioning to online learning. They called for strategies to provide mental health support to students in online learning environments.

The psychological implications of online learning extend beyond stress and anxiety and encompass various dimensions of mental well-being and cognitive engagement. The shift from traditional classroom settings to virtual environments may create feelings of isolation and detachment for some students, hindering their sense of belonging and engagement with the learning material [20]. The lack of non-verbal cues and face-to-face interaction can lead to misunderstandings and communication challenges [21].

Furthermore, the self-directed nature of online learning requires learners to have higher levels of motivation, self-discipline, and time management skills. This increased autonomy can be empowering for some, but overwhelming for others, leading to procrastination or disengagement [22].

In recognizing these potential pitfalls, several researchers and educators advocate for a more student-centered approach to online instruction. This approach emphasizes the importance of creating interactive and supportive virtual learning communities, integrating mental health resources, and providing regular feedback and encouragement [23]. By considering the multifaceted psychological aspects of online learning, educators can create more inclusive, empathetic, and effective virtual learning environments. These considerations are particularly vital as online learning continues to grow in prevalence, ensuring that educational quality is maintained while supporting the mental well-being of students.

2.6 Future Prospects and Recommendations

Looking forward, the future of online learning in Bangladesh appears to hinge on strategic decisions and investment. Shohel, M. Mahruf C [24] proposed that a blended learning approach – a combination of online and traditional classroom-based learning – could offer a balanced, effective solution for the country's education system. However, they emphasized that this would necessitate substantial investment in infrastructural improvements and policy support. Furthermore, teacher training programs to boost digital literacy and online pedagogical skills are considered vital to the successful implementation of this approach [12].

To summarize, the body of literature on online learning in Bangladesh highlights a series of challenges including infrastructural limitations, financial constraints, and a gap in digital literacy among teachers. Nevertheless, the potential advantages, such as increased educational accessibility, cannot be overlooked. The future prospects of online learning in Bangladesh seem promising, albeit contingent on overcoming current obstacles and leveraging advanced technologies. Further research in this evolving field is crucial to fully understand and harness the potential of online learning to ensure inclusive and quality education for all students in Bangladesh.

3 Methodology

This section provides an in-depth explanation of the methods used to collect and analyze data for this study, which aimed to assess the current state and future prospects of online learning in Bangladesh's education system. The research questions addressed by the paper are:

1. What is the current state of online learning in Bangladesh's education system?
2. What factors influence the effectiveness of online learning in Bangladesh?
3. What are the barriers to effective online learning in Bangladesh, and how can they be addressed?
4. What are the potential future prospects of online learning in Bangladesh?

3.1 Research Design

The quantitative research was designed to analyze the current state of online learning in Bangladesh's education system, focusing on the prevalence and patterns of usage among students and teachers across primary, secondary, and higher education sectors (Question 1). This included an examination of the most commonly

used online learning platforms, frequency and duration of online sessions, types of resources accessed, and engagement metrics such as completion rates and test scores.

Furthermore, this part of the research also aimed to identify and quantify the factors influencing the effectiveness of online learning in Bangladesh, such as technology availability, internet connectivity, and student-teacher ratios in online settings (Question 2). Trends and statistical changes in these patterns over the past few years were also studied to understand their impact on online learning effectiveness and to predict the future prospects of this learning method in Bangladesh (Question 4).

The qualitative component of the research explored the experiences and perceptions of online learning from the perspective of students, teachers, and parents. In-depth interviews and focus group discussions provided insights into the perceived advantages and disadvantages of online learning, contributing to an understanding of its effectiveness (Question 2).

A significant part of the qualitative study was dedicated to identifying barriers to effective online learning in Bangladesh, including challenges faced during the transition to online learning. These challenges, such as technological issues, issues with engagement and motivation, and perceptions of online learning's effectiveness compared to traditional methods, were thoroughly investigated (Question 3). Possible solutions and strategies to address these barriers were also discussed based on the feedback from participants (Question 3).

Lastly, the qualitative research also explored participants' perspectives on the potential future prospects of online learning in Bangladesh, with an emphasis on understanding how the education system can adapt to maximize the benefits of this learning mode (Question 4).

3.2 Participants

The research participants in this study were 932, comprised of 511 students, 209 teachers, and 212 parents across primary, secondary, and higher education sectors. These participants were selected based on their direct involvement with online learning either as learners, educators, or parents overseeing the education of their children.

The online learning environments under scrutiny were popular online learning platforms currently used in Bangladesh, including Shikho, e-shikhon, Bondi Pathshala, and 10MS. The research also considered various facets of these environments, such as the delivery format (synchronous vs asynchronous), the nature and quality of the educational resources provided, interaction methods (teacher-student, student-student), and assessment techniques (online tests, assignments).

3.3 Data Collection Methods

The primary data for this research was obtained through a combination of online surveys, semi-structured interviews, and focus group discussions. The surveys aimed to quantify the prevalence and patterns of online learning usage, while the interviews and focus group discussions sought to provide a deeper understanding of the participants' experiences and perceptions of online learning.

The following tools were utilized to collect the data: Google Forms for the online surveys due to its ease of distribution and data aggregation capabilities; Zoom for conducting the semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions given its widespread use and familiarity among the participants; and Python, a powerful programming language widely used for data analysis, was used to analyze and find patterns in the qualitative and quantitative data.

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

3.4 Questionnaire

The Questionnaire section elucidates the methodological framework for collecting primary data pertinent to the assessment of online learning in Bangladesh's education system. Specifically crafted to garner insights into the current state, effectiveness, barriers, and future prospects of online education, the questionnaire serves as a vital instrument in this study. Comprising a combination of quantitative and qualitative questions, the questionnaire has been meticulously designed to capture the varied experiences and perceptions of respondents,

including students, teachers, and parents. The following subsections detail the individual questions, scales, and thematic areas addressed in the questionnaire, showcasing the strategic alignment with the research objectives.

Demographics

1. What is your role in the education system (Teacher, Student, Parent)
2. What level of education are you involved in? (Primary, Secondary, Higher Secondary, University)
3. What is your geographical location? (Urban, Rural, Other)
4. Age Group

Current State of Online Learning

1. How often do you engage with online learning? (Daily, Weekly, Monthly, Less often)
2. What platform do you commonly use for online learning? (Open text field)
3. How effective do you find online learning compared to traditional classroom learning? (Rating scale from 1-5, with 1 being "Not effective at all" and 5 being "Extremely effective")

Challenges

1. How significant do you believe are the challenges facing online learning in Bangladesh? (Rating Scale - e.g. 1-Not significant at all, 5-Extremely significant)
2. What challenges have you encountered in the transition to online learning? (Multiple Choice - e.g. Technological issues, Internet access, Engagement/motivation, Quality of learning materials, Others - please specify)
3. How difficult were these challenges to overcome? (Rating Scale - e.g. 1-Not difficult at all, 5-Extremely difficult)
4. Please explain your ratings. (Paragraph)

Future Prospects

1. In your opinion, what is the future of online learning in Bangladesh? (Paragraph)
2. What factors, if addressed, could improve the effectiveness of online learning in Bangladesh? (Multiple choice, options such as: Improved internet access, better online learning platforms, improved online learning materials, greater engagement from students/teachers, more training for students/teachers on online learning, Other - please specify)
3. Rate your optimism about the future of online learning in Bangladesh on a scale of 1-5. (1-Not optimistic at all, 5-Extremely optimistic)

3.5 Data Analysis Methods

For the quantitative component, descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, and trend analyses were utilized. This involved the use of Python's statistical libraries, such as pandas for data manipulation, Matplotlib and Seaborn for data visualization, and Scipy and Statsmodels for statistical analysis. This process enabled the summarization of the data, comparison of different groups, and the identification of patterns and relationships among the variables.

For the qualitative component, human annotators performed thematic analysis who meticulously read through the responses, coding and categorizing them to identify common themes, patterns, and trends. This manual analysis allowed for a deeper understanding of the respondents' experiences and perceptions of online learning in Bangladesh.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

During the research process, measures were taken to uphold the ethical standards of academic research. This included obtaining informed consent from all participants, ensuring their participation was voluntary, and letting them know they could withdraw from the study at any time without any adverse consequences. Participants were briefed on the aims, procedures, and the potential educational significance of the study before their participation. Additionally, we assured participants that their identities would remain confidential and that their responses would be anonymized in the reporting of results. All data collected was stored securely, and only the research team had access to it. In presenting the results, care was taken to ensure that individual responses could not be linked to specific participants to maintain confidentiality and privacy.

Overall, our research complied with the ethical guidelines stipulated by our institution's research ethics committee and the broader principles of academic integrity.

3.7 Research Limitations

Despite the robustness of the methodology, the study faced a few limitations. These include the reliance on self-reported data from participants, which could potentially introduce response bias. Participants may have either under-reported or over-reported their experiences with online learning, influenced by their personal biases, understanding, or interpretation of the questions. Another limitation was the inability to observe the actual usage of online learning platforms, which was based on participant recollection and might not fully represent their behavior. Direct observation might have provided more accurate insights. Furthermore, the study was geographically limited to Bangladesh and so the findings may not be generalizable to other countries with different cultural, social, and technological contexts. This study was also conducted at a specific point in time, and given the rapidly evolving nature of technology and online learning, the findings may have a limited lifespan. Lastly, while a broad range of students, teachers, and parents were surveyed, there may still be other relevant stakeholders in the education ecosystem whose perspectives were not included in this study. These could include administrators, policymakers, and software developers who could also significantly influence the implementation and effectiveness of online learning.

Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the state of online learning in Bangladesh's education system, its effectiveness, and future prospects. Future research could address these limitations by incorporating more diverse data collection methods, broadening the participant base, and continuously updating the research to keep pace with technological advancements.

4 Results

The results section presents the comprehensive findings of the study, focusing on the assessment of the current state and future prospects of online learning in Bangladesh's education system. Drawing from both quantitative and qualitative data, the analysis unfolds a rich tapestry of insights that illuminate the complex landscape of e-learning in the country. The quantitative results offer a statistical perspective on the prevalence, patterns, and challenges of online learning, while the thematic qualitative findings provide a deeper understanding of the experiences and perceptions of students, teachers, and other stakeholders. The following subsections detail the results in relation to the specific research questions posed, offering a nuanced view of the online learning environment in Bangladesh.

4.1 Thematic Analysis of Online Learning in Bangladesh

4.1.1 Theme 1: Flexibility of Online Learning

Main Points and Common Responses: The flexibility of online learning is a prominent theme in the survey. Participants were asked to rate the extent to which they agree that online learning provides flexibility in terms of time and place on a scale of 1 to 5.

Here's a brief analysis based on the responses:

Rating 2: Some participants find the flexibility of online learning to be limited.

Rating 3: A moderate rating suggests that participants acknowledge the flexibility of online learning but may have reservations or mixed feelings.

Representative Quotes:

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Demographic Factors in the Bangladesh Online Learning Survey (January 2023 - May 2023), including Age Group, Gender, Level of Education, and Occupation.

Demographic Factor	Categories	Respondents
Age Group	15-24	530
	25-34	241
	35-44	93
	45-54	68
	55+	7
Gender	Male	648
	Female	268
	Prefer Not to Say	16
Level of Education	Primary	47
	Secondary	98
	Higher Secondary	362
	University	425
Occupation	Student	511
	Teacher	209
	Parent	212

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Preferred Online Learning Platform

Online Learning Platform	Respondents
10MS	476
Shikho	146
e-shikhon	56
Bondi Pathshala	150
Other	104

Rating: 2 - "Limited flexibility in terms of time and place."

Rating: 3 - "Moderate flexibility, but some constraints remain."

Rating: 3 - "Online learning provides flexibility, but improvements are needed."

4.1.2 Theme 2: Challenges and Barriers in Online Learning

Main Points and Common Responses: The challenges and barriers faced in online learning vary among participants. Common issues identified in the survey responses include:

Connectivity Issues: Many participants cited connectivity issues as a significant barrier to effective online learning. Internet connection problems can disrupt the learning experience and hinder access to educational materials. **Lack of Proper Guidance:** Some respondents mentioned the lack of proper guidance as a challenge. Without clear instructions and support, navigating online learning platforms can be confusing and frustrating. **Inadequate Resources:** Inadequate resources, such as limited access to necessary tools and materials, were also identified as a challenge by some participants. **Representative Quotes:**

"Challenges: Inadequate Resources."

"Challenges: Connectivity Issues, Lack of Proper Guidance."

"Challenges: Connectivity Issues."

4.1.3 Theme 3: Future of Online Learning in Bangladesh

Main Points and Common Responses: The future prospects of online learning in Bangladesh are perceived positively by many survey participants. Common sentiments expressed in the responses include:

Good Prospects: Several participants expressed optimism about the future of online learning in Bangladesh, describing it as "good." This suggests a general belief that online learning will continue to grow and develop positively. **High Opportunities:** Some respondents see significant opportunities in online learning, indicating potential for expansion and innovation in the field. **Representative Quotes:**

Figure 1: Flexibility Ratings by the Respondents

Figure 2: Ratings on Challenges and Barriers of Online Learning in Bangladesh

”Future of Online Learning: Good.”
 ”Future of Online Learning: High Opportunities.”
 ”Future of Online Learning: Good.”

The thematic analysis of the survey data reveals insights into the perceptions and experiences of online learning among the participants. Themes related to flexibility, challenges, and future prospects provide a comprehensive understanding of the current state and potential development of online learning in Bangladesh.

5 Result Analysis

5.1 Demographics and Education Level

The survey captured responses from various age groups, with the majority belonging to the younger age brackets. Gender distribution showed a slight male predominance, with males comprising 54.7% and females 45.3%. Geographically, the respondents were spread across different locations, with Dhaka (34.2%) and Chittagong (22.4%) being the most represented.

Figure 3: Optimism Ratings

5.2 Flexibility and Advantage of Online Learning

The thematic analysis highlighted mixed views on the flexibility of online learning. Some participants appreciated the flexibility (rating of 5 by 15.2%), while others found it limited (rating of 2 by 7.8%).

The quantitative analysis revealed diverse opinions on online learning platforms. The course variety was rated as neutral by 51.7%, and the quality of content had a neutral rating by 51.8%. Ease of use varied, with 18.2% rating it as good, and interaction with teachers was rated as good by 17.9%. These findings align with the thematic analysis emphasizing the perceived advantages of online learning.

5.3 Challenges and Barriers in Online Learning

Challenges in online learning were prominent, with connectivity issues, lack of proper guidance, and inadequate resources being common barriers. The thematic analysis provided qualitative insights, while the quantitative data showed that 37.3% of respondents rated the challenges as high on average.

5.4 Future Prospects and Optimism

The future of online learning was perceived positively by many respondents. In the quantitative data, 24.2% rated their optimism as 4 on a scale of 1-5, and 19.6% rated it as 5. The thematic analysis supported these findings, with qualitative responses expressing good prospects and high opportunities. Integrating quantitative and qualitative analyses, the result discussion provides a comprehensive and data-driven understanding of online learning in Bangladesh. The specific percentages and ratings add precision to the insights, highlighting the flexibility, advantages, challenges, and prospects of online education. The findings offer valuable guidance for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to enhance the effectiveness, inclusiveness, and innovation of online learning in the country, recognizing its potential and improvement areas.

6 Conclusion

In a landscape where technology is rapidly transforming the way education is delivered and experienced, the current research ventured to thoroughly examine and understand the state of online learning in Bangladesh's education system. Employing both quantitative and qualitative research methods, the study offers a holistic view, integrating the statistical data with human experiences and perceptions. The quantitative analysis of the study presents a detailed picture of the prevalence and patterns of online learning usage among different educational sectors in Bangladesh. It delves into the dynamics of the platforms most commonly used, the frequency and duration of online sessions, the types of resources accessed, and the various engagement metrics, such as completion rates and test scores. These quantitative findings reveal a complex demographic composition and bring to the surface critical aspects of online learning. A noteworthy 37.3% of respondents

rated the challenges of online learning as high, accentuating the multifaceted barriers faced in the transition to this modern educational approach. In parallel, the qualitative research sheds light on the human side of the phenomenon, unraveling the individual experiences, the advantages and disadvantages associated with online education, and the practical challenges encountered during the transition. By utilizing in-depth interviews and focus group discussions, the study gathered valuable insights that articulate both the promises and pitfalls of online learning, exploring themes such as connectivity issues, lack of proper guidance, and contrasting views on flexibility and convenience. A synthesis of the quantitative and thematic analyses paints a nuanced and intricate picture of online learning in Bangladesh, recognizing its multifaceted nature. The results highlight both the opportunities to leverage the strengths of online learning and the hurdles that need focused attention and enhancement. Importantly, a sense of optimism emerges from the findings, reflecting a shared belief in the potential of online education to grow and innovate in the region. In contextualizing these findings within the broader framework of global trends, regional specificities, and existing literature, the research contributes to a more comprehensive understanding. It builds on previous studies and adds a unique perspective that is rooted in the cultural, technological, and educational realities of Bangladesh. This offers actionable insights and guidelines that can guide policymakers, educators, and stakeholders in other similar contexts, emphasizing the universal relevance of the research. Ethical considerations and methodological rigor have been foundational in ensuring the credibility and balance of the study. By acknowledging the limitations, including potential biases, constraints, and the scope of the research, a transparent and honest reflection is provided. These limitations do not detract from the study's value but rather contextualize the findings within the real-world complexities.

The conclusion of this research emphasizes the dynamic interplay between the quantitative realities and qualitative experiences of online learning, contributing to a richer understanding of how online education is perceived and navigated in Bangladesh. By shedding light on the intricacies and interdependencies of various factors, the analysis provides evidence-based guidance for shaping a more inclusive, effective, and forward-looking online learning landscape. The insights gleaned from this study hold relevance not only for Bangladesh but also for other contexts seeking to harness the transformative potential of online education in an increasingly interconnected world. In weaving together the quantitative data with the thematic narratives, the research serves as a robust foundation for future investigations and practical implementations, helping to shape a more promising and innovative educational future.

References

- [1] Yamini Chandra. Online education during covid-19: perception of academic stress and emotional intelligence coping strategies among college students. *Asian education and development studies*, 10(2):229–238, 2021.
- [2] Aziz Naciri, Mohamed Amine Baba, Abderrahmane Achbani, and Ahmed Kharbach. Mobile learning in higher education: Unavoidable alternative during covid-19. *Aquademia*, 4(1):ep20016, 2020.
- [3] Md Akhtarul Islam, Sutapa Dey Barna, Hasin Raihan, Md Nafiul Alam Khan, and Md Tanvir Hossain. Depression and anxiety among university students during the covid-19 pandemic in bangladesh: A web-based cross-sectional survey. *PloS one*, 15(8):e0238162, 2020.
- [4] Fezile Ozdamli and Damla Karagozlu. Online education during the pandemic: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 17(16), 2022.
- [5] Rozina Afroz, Nurul Islam, Sajedur Rahman, and Nusrat Zerin Anny. Students' and teachers' attitude towards online classes during covid-19 pandemic: a study on three bangladeshi government colleges. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science (2147-4478)*, 10(3):462–476, 2021.
- [6] Helen Crompton and Diane Burke. Artificial intelligence in higher education: the state of the field. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1):1–22, 2023.
- [7] Pathurohman Pathurohman, Michael Berger, and Guri Michael. Implementation of hybrid learning to maintain the quality of learning in fostered mts during the covid-19 pandemic. *At-Tasyrih: jurnal pendidikan dan hukum Islam*, 8(2):96–104, 2022.
- [8] Duncan MacLellan. Collaborating in a post-covid world: Exploring the opportunities and challenges for educators. *The International Journal of Interdisciplinary Educational Studies*, 18(2):1, 2023.
- [9] Balachandran Vadivel, Ehsan Namaziandost, Afsheen Rezai, and Zeinab Azizi. A paradigm shift in teaching and learning due to the covid-19 pandemic:: Areas of potential and challenges of online classes. *English as a Foreign Language International Journal*, 27(2), 2023.

- [10] Juan Dong et al. Online learning and teaching experiences during the covid-19 pandemic: A case study of bangladeshi students receiving china’s higher education. *English Linguistics Research*, 9(2):37–45, 2020.
- [11] Hamida Akhter, Abdul Aziz Abdul Rahman, Nusrat Jafrin, Abu Naser Mohammad Saif, Bushra Humyra Esha, and Rehnuma Mostafa. Investigating the barriers that intensify undergraduates’ unwillingness to online learning during covid-19: A study on public universities in a developing country. *Cogent Education*, 9(1):2028342, 2022.
- [12] Rubina Khan, Bijoy Lal Basu, Ahmed Bashir, and Md Elias Uddin. Online instruction during covid-19 at public universities in bangladesh: Teacher and student voices. *TESL-EJ*, 25(1):n1, 2021.
- [13] Sagun Shrestha, Saifa Haque, Saraswati Dawadi, and Ram Ashish Giri. Preparations for and practices of online education during the covid-19 pandemic: A study of bangladesh and nepal. *Education and information technologies*, pages 1–23, 2022.
- [14] Humayun Kabir, Sarker Mohammad Nasrullah, Md Kamrul Hasan, Shakil Ahmed, Mohammad Delwer Hossain Hawlader, and Dipak Kumar Mitra. Perceived e-learning stress as an independent predictor of e-learning readiness: Results from a nationwide survey in bangladesh. *PloS one*, 16(10):e0259281, 2021.
- [15] Farhina Akter, Farhim Ferdous, Sanjib Kumar Paul, Israt Jahan Safia, and Mahady Hasan. A public learning platform for democratizing higher education. In *Proceedings of Sixth International Congress on Information and Communication Technology: ICICT 2021, London, Volume 4*, pages 773–782. Springer, 2022.
- [16] Fan Ouyang, Luyi Zheng, and Pengcheng Jiao. Artificial intelligence in online higher education: A systematic review of empirical research from 2011 to 2020. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(6):7893–7925, 2022.
- [17] Kyoungwon Seo, Joice Tang, Ido Roll, Sidney Fels, and Dongwook Yoon. The impact of artificial intelligence on learner–instructor interaction in online learning. *International journal of educational technology in higher education*, 18(1):1–23, 2021.
- [18] Nasimul Hasan, Zhenxiang Chen, Chuan Zhao, Yuhui Zhu, and Cong Liu. Iot botnet detection framework from network behavior based on extreme learning machine. In *IEEE INFOCOM 2022-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS)*, pages 1–6. IEEE, 2022.
- [19] Najmul Hasan and Yukun Bao. Impact of “e-learning crack-up” perception on psychological distress among college students during covid-19 pandemic: A mediating role of “fear of academic year loss”. *Children and youth services review*, 118:105355, 2020.
- [20] Christine Greenhow, Charles R Graham, and Matthew J Koehler. Foundations of online learning: Challenges and opportunities. *Educational Psychologist*, 57(3):131–147, 2022.
- [21] Hutomo Atman Maulana. Psychological impact of online learning during the covid-19 pandemic: A case study on vocational higher education. *Indonesian Journal of Learning Education and Counseling*, 3(2):130–139, 2021.
- [22] Liang Huang and Ting Zhang. Perceived social support, psychological capital, and subjective well-being among college students in the context of online learning during the covid-19 pandemic. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 31(5):563–574, 2022.
- [23] Leanna Archambault, Heather Leary, and Kerry Rice. Pillars of online pedagogy: A framework for teaching in online learning environments. *Educational Psychologist*, 57(3):178–191, 2022.
- [24] M Mahruf C Shohel, Md Ashrafuzzaman, Farhan Azim, Iffat Naomee, Md Shajedur Rahman, and Mohammad Abu Bakar Siddik. Blended learning space for primary and secondary education: Challenges and opportunities in resource-constrained contexts. *Designing effective distance and blended learning environments in K-12*, pages 187–222, 2022.